

BODY LANGUAGE TABOO

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What body language means? Body language is a range of nonverbal signals that you can use to communicate your feelings and intention. These include your posture, facial expressions, and hand gestures. Your ability to understand and interpret other people's body language can help you to pick up on unspoken issues or feelings.

Body language is a type of communication in which physical behavior, as opposed to words, are used to express or convey information. Such behavior includes facial expressions, body posture, gestures, eye movement, touch and the use of space. The term body language is usually applied in regard to people but may also be applied in regard to people but may also be applied to animals. The study of body language is also known as kinesics. Although body language is an important part of communication, most of it happens without conscious awareness. Body "language" must not be confused with sign language. Sign languages are literally languages: they have (their own) complex grammar systems, and they also are able to exhibit the fundamental properties that are considered to exist in all (true) languages. Body language, on the other hand, does not have grammar system and must be interpreted broadly, instead of having an absolute meaning corresponding with a certain movement, so it is not a language, and is simply termed as a "language" due to popular culture.

In a society, there are agreed-upon interpretations of particular behavior. Interpretations may vary from country to country, or culture to culture (on this note, there also is controversy on whether body language is universal)

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Body language a subset of nonverbal communication

complements verbal communication in social interaction. In fact, some researchers concluded that nonverbal communication accounts for the majority of information transmitted during interpersonal interactions. It helps to establish the relationship between two people and regulates

What is body language examples

Examples for body language include facial expressions, eye gaze, gestures, posture and body movements, in many cases, the things we don't say can convey volumes of information.

The tips given in this article are a good general guide for interpreting body language, but they won't apply to everyone.

For example, people may have a different cultural background from you and positive gestures in one country can be negative in others

The many different types of nonverbal communication or body language include:

*Facial expressions. The human face is extremely expressive, able to convey countless emotions without saying a word...

Body movement and posture...

Gestures...

Eye contact...

Touch...

Space...

Voice...

Pay attention to inconsistencies.

Taboo- a social or religious custom prohibiting or restricting a particular practice or forbidding association with a particular person, place, or thing. "Many taboos have developed around physical exposure"

Definitions from Oxford languages book

<https://www.verywellmind.com>

Body language Project: <https://www.mindtools.com>.

<https://www.helpguide.org...>

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